

PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

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HISTORY OF SERIES THEORY: FROM BINOMIAL FORMULA OF ISAAC NEWTON TO SOLUTION OF BASEL PROBLEM BY LEONHARD EULER

Abstract.

The given paper presents some historical facts from theory of functional, power, and number series, as well as history of solving of so-called Basel problem. This problem is rather famous question in the history of mathematics, named after the city in Switzerland, where world-famous mathematician Leonhard Euler studied. The problem asks for exact sum of reciprocals of squares of natural numbers.

Keywords: *functional series, power series, number series, Isaac Newton, Brook Taylor, Colin Maclaurin, Leonhard Euler, Basel problem.*

Many mathematical problems are either solved by calculating values of functions and integrals, or reduced to solving differential equations, containing derivatives or differentials of unknown functions. However, exact execution of these mathematical operations in many cases is difficult or impossible. In some cases, it is possible to obtain approximate solution to these problems with desired accuracy, using functional, or, more precisely, power series. Because such series are simple

and, at the same time, perfect tool from mathematical analysis for approximate calculation of functions, integrals, and finding solutions of differential equations. In connection with this, theory of functional series was created in close connection with theory of approximate representation of functions in the form of polynomials. It was first done by Isaac Newton (1642 – 1727) in 1676.

Fig. 1. Isaac Newton – English physicist and mathematician

In his letter to the Secretary of the Royal Society of London the next formula appeared

$$(1+x)^m = 1 + \frac{m}{1!}x + \frac{m(m-1)}{2!}x^2 + \frac{m(m-1)(m-2)}{3!}x^3 + \dots + x^m,$$

that is known nowadays as Newton's binomial formula. Here we see the function $(1+x)^m$, represented as polynomial. But if number m is not natural, the right-

hand side of the formula above turns out not to be polynomial, but some infinite sum of terms, depending on x , i.e. we see functional series.

Developing Newton's idea, English mathematician Brook Taylor (1685 – 1731) proved in 1715 that any function, having derivatives of all orders at x_0 , can be compared with power series of the form

$$f(x) \sim f(x_0) + \frac{f'(x_0)}{1!}(x - x_0) + \frac{f''(x_0)}{2!}(x - x_0)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(x_0)}{n!}(x - x_0)^n + \dots$$

$$+ \frac{f'''(x_0)}{3!}(x - x_0)^3 +$$

Fig. 2. Brook Taylor – English mathematician and barrister

We cannot yet equate this function f with the function from the right-hand side. In order to replace the sign of equivalence « \sim » with the sign of equation « $=$ », it is necessary to carry out several additional arguments, related specifically to infinity of number of slogans in the right-hand side of the equality and concerning domain of this series.

At $x = 0$ the Taylor formula takes the form of the Maclaurin formula

$$f(x) \sim f(0) + \frac{f'(0)}{1!}x + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}x^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}x^3 + \dots$$

$$+ \frac{f^{(n)}(0)}{n!}x^n + \dots$$

Colin Maclaurin (1698 – 1746), famous student of Newton, in his work «A Treatise on Fluxions» in 1742 established that series, expressing an analytical function, is unique one, and this will be the Taylor series, generated by such a function.

Fig. 3. Colin Maclaurin – Scottish mathematician

So, functional series appeared in the XVIII century as way of representing functions that allow infinite differentiation. However, any function, represented by series, was not named its sum, and generally at that time there were only attempts to introduce the concept of

sum of series. For example, Leonhard Euler (1707 – 1783), having written out the corresponding power series for some function, gave to every variable x specific value of x_0 .

Fig. 4. Leonhard Euler – one of the greatest mathematicians and physicists of all time

The result was numerical series. Euler considered the sum of this series to be the value of the original function at point x_0 . But this is not always true. Niels Henrik Abel (1802 – 1829) named divergent series as «diabolical invention».

Fig. 5. Niels Henrik Abel – Norwegian mathematician

Scientists began to guess that divergent series has no sum only in the XIX century, although in the XVIII century many, and above all Euler, worked on concepts of convergence and divergence. In 1768 French mathematician and philosopher Jean Baptiste D'Alembert

(1717 – 1783) investigated relation of the next term to the previous one in binomial series and showed that if this relation is modulo less than one, then series converges.

Fig. 6. Jean Baptiste D'Alembert – French mathematician, physicist, and philosopher

He proved a theorem, stating sign of convergence of positive series in general terms, now known as the D'Alembert sign. Euler named series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_n$ convergent if its general term u_n , $n \geq 1$, tends to zero with unlimited increase of n . In theory of divergent series he

has obtained many results, but these results were not applied for a long time. Euler's results were justified only at the end of the XIX century. French scientist Augustin Louis Cauchy (1789 – 1857) played major role in formation of concept of sum of convergent series.

Fig. 7. Augustin Louis Cauchy – French mathematician, engineer, and physicist

He did a lot not only in theory of series, but also in theory of limits, in development of the very concept of limit. In 1826 Cauchy stated that divergent series has no sum.

The next fact is story from numeric series theory – interesting fact about so-called Basel problem. In history of mathematics there are many cases when someone stated some problem to the whole mathematical

world, but this problem remained unsolved for decades or even centuries. Often new areas of mathematics appeared while solving such a problem. This story is about one of such cases – about so-called Basel problem, which was posed as challenge to European mathematicians in 1644 and remained open for ninety years.

Fig. 8. Modern Basel – city in northwestern Switzerland on the River Rhine

It resisted all attempts to solve it until young Euler finally found the answer to it in 1734. During his life, he would present several different solvings to the problem. Here we present idea of one, very simple and elegant. Indeed, this Euler's solution is work of amazing ingenuity, although general level of mathematics in it does not exceed course of elementary algebra for high school.

So-called Basel problem is formulated very simply: we need to find exact value of the next sum

$$1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2}$$

As with all other infinite series, the question arises for this series whether it converges to any finite value. The fact that its terms become infinitesimal is not sufficient to ensure convergence. For example, the following series

$$1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}$$

has infinite sum, i.e. it diverges, despite the fact that its terms become arbitrarily small. However, for series of inverse squares it was previously shown that it converges to some number less than two, but exact value to which it converges was not known.

For many years, two brothers Bernoulli have been trying to solve this problem, but they were not suc-

cessful. Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz has also been working on this problem for many years and has got no result.

Fig. 9. Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz – German philosopher, mathematician, and political adviser

Finally, young Euler in 1734 proposed the next idea.

In order to begin, let's consider one algebraic equation of the fourth degree

$$x^4 + a_1x^3 + a_2x^2 + a_3x + a_4 = 0.$$

Assume that its roots are $b, c, d,$ and e . Then we can decompose the polynomial from the left-hand side into four linear factors and obtain the next equation

$$(x - b)(x - c)(x - d)(x - e) = 0,$$

where from

$$(b - x)(c - x)(d - x)(e - x) = 0.$$

If none of these four roots is zero, we can rewrite this equation in the next form

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(b - x)(c - x)(d - x)(e - x)}{bcde} \\ &= \frac{b - x}{b} \frac{c - x}{c} \frac{d - x}{d} \frac{e - x}{e} = \\ &= \left(\frac{b - x}{b} - \frac{x}{b}\right) \left(\frac{c - x}{c} - \frac{x}{c}\right) \left(\frac{d - x}{d} - \frac{x}{d}\right) \left(\frac{e - x}{e} - \frac{x}{e}\right) \\ &= \left(1 - \frac{x}{b}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x}{c}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x}{d}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x}{e}\right) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Newton has found out that $\sin x$ can be rewritten with the help of polynomial of endless power, i.e. – with the help of power series of the form

$$\sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \frac{x^7}{7!} + \dots$$

Now, if we divide both sides by x , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sin x}{x} &= \frac{x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \frac{x^7}{7!} + \dots}{x} \\ &= \frac{x}{x} - \frac{\frac{x^3}{3!}}{x} + \frac{\frac{x^5}{5!}}{x} - \frac{\frac{x^7}{7!}}{x} + \dots = \\ &= 1 - \frac{x^2}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{5!} - \frac{x^6}{7!} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

We know all zeros of $\sin x$, they are $0, \pm\pi, \pm2\pi, \pm3\pi, \dots$. We also know from the factorization theorem of Karl Weierstrass that every entire function can be represented as product, involving its zeroes.

Fig. 10. Karl Weierstrass – German mathematician, one of the founders of modern theory of functions

Euler's first idea was to assume that this theorem is true for infinite polynomials, i.e. to rewrite

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sin x}{x} &= \left(1 - \frac{x}{\pi}\right) \left(1 + \frac{x}{\pi}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x}{2\pi}\right) \left(1 + \frac{x}{2\pi}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x}{3\pi}\right) \left(1 + \frac{x}{3\pi}\right) \dots = \\ &= \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{4\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{9\pi^2}\right) \dots \end{aligned}$$

So, Euler has got that infinite sum is equal to infinite product. Although this product consists of infinite number of factors, we can figure out what coefficient will be near each power. In order to do it let us consider the next finite product:

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b)(c + d)(e + f) &= ace + acf + ade + adf + bce \\ &+ bcf + bde + bdf. \end{aligned}$$

When opening all brackets in this product, each element, for example, ace , is equal to product of terms, taken from each bracket on the left, one at time. So, Euler saw that after formal multiplying this infinite product out and collecting terms near x^2 , the corresponding coefficient near x^2 will be equal to

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(-1 - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{16} - \dots\right) \frac{1}{\pi^2}, \\ \text{so} &\left(-1 - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{16} - \dots\right) \frac{1}{\pi^2} = -\frac{1}{3!} \end{aligned}$$

therefore, after multiplying both sides of this equation by π^2 , we get

$$-1 - \frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{16} - \dots = -\frac{\pi^2}{3!}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \dots &= 1 + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{16} + \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{3!} \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{6}. \end{aligned}$$

Using similar methods, Euler has also showed in his historical work that

$$1 + \frac{1}{2^4} + \frac{1}{3^4} + \frac{1}{4^4} + \dots = \frac{\pi^4}{90}$$

and

$$1 + \frac{1}{2^6} + \frac{1}{3^6} + \frac{1}{4^6} + \dots = \frac{\pi^6}{945}$$

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